

Amides and Schiff Bases from 4-Amino Isoxazoles and their Physiological Activity.

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Starting from 3-methyl-4-amino-5-styryl isoxazoles, obtained by the reduction of 3-methyl-4-nitro-5-styryl isoxazoles, amides and Schiff bases have been prepared. The compounds have been tested for bacteriostatic and fungistatic activities.

A CYLAMINO heterocycles gained prominence as pharmacologically important substances with the isolation of navobiocin¹ and coumermycin². Anticancer Schiff bases³ have been prepared by condensing aniline with some substituted benzaldehydes. The well known antibiotic cycloserine⁴, which is 4-amino-3-isoxazolidone, has also been utilized in the synthesis of Schiff bases⁵ and amides⁶ exhibiting varied physiological activities. A careful literature survey revealed that no such amides or Schiff bases have been investigated in the isoxazole series excepting those from cycloserine (loc. cit). Hence with a view to evaluating the antibacterial and antifungal properties, the preparation of a few amides and Schiff bases from amino isoxazoles was taken up. The present investigation describes the preparation of amides and Schiff bases derived from 3-methyl-5-styryl-4-amino isoxazoles.

Amino isoxazoles were obtained starting from 3,5-dimethyl isoxazole⁷ (I, Chart 1). Nitration of the latter with fuming nitric and conc. sulphuric acids furnished 3,5-dimethyl-4-nitro isoxazole⁷. Condensa-

tion of the foregoing nitro isoxazole containing on activated 5-methyl with a few benzaldehydes in methanol in the presence of traces of piperidine gave crystalline 3-methyl-4-nitro-5-styryl isoxazoles⁸. The nitro group can bestow resonance stabilization to the anion (IV) of the 5-methyl only and not to that of the 3-methyl. Convincing spectroscopic evidence⁹ has also been put forth by us in favour of the exclusive formation of the 5-styryl compound. Though the 3-methyl group is associated with-C=N- of the isoxazole, the electron withdrawing power and hence the anion stabilizing capacity of the C=N- is low in comparison to that of the nitro group which exerts influence on the 5-methyl only. The homogeneity of the 5-styryl compound, confirmed by the TLC purity, unequivocally ruled out the formation of the 3-styryl compound. The rationale behind having a styrene moiety in these compounds is that the styrenes have been reported to be active against pathogenic fungi¹⁰ and *Pericularia oryzae*¹¹.

Reduction of the nitro compound (III) to 3-methyl-4-amino-5-styryl isoxazole (V) was effected with stannous chloride and hydrochloric acid or sodium dithionite in

Chart I

I = 3,5-Dimethyl isoxazole ;
III = 3-Methyl-4-nitro-5-styryl isoxazole ;
V = 3-Methyl-4-amino-5-styryl isoxazole ;
VII = 3-Methyl-4-acylamino-5-styryl isoxazole ;

II = 3,5-Dimethyl-4-nitro-isoxazole ;
IV = Resonating forms of the anion of 3,5-dimethyl-4-nitro isoxazole ;
VI = Schiff base from 3-Methyl-4-amino-5-styryl-isoxazole

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ammonia. The authors earlier gave chemical as well as spectroscopic evidence^{1,2} to the effect that during the reduction, the double bond of the styryl group was unaffected. The next step in the investigation is the conversion of the amino isoxazoles to the title compounds. The acylamino isoxazole (VI) was obtained by the treatment of the amino isoxazole with various acid chlorides in the presence of 10% sodium hydroxide at room temperature. The yields of these amides (see the Table) ranged from 75-85%. The Schiff bases (VII) were prepared by the condensation of the amino isoxazoles with a few benzaldehydes in boiling alcohol. The products (see the Table) separated in crystalline form in almost quantitative yields.

was stirred at room temperature with the acid chloride (.006 mole) in the presence of 10% sodium hydroxide for about 10-15 min. The separated product was washed with water and crystallized from methanol (mps and analytical data in the Table).

2. *Preparation of the Schiff bases (VII) :*

3-Methyl-4-amino-5-styryl isoxazole (.005 mole) and benzaldehyde (.005 mole) were refluxed in methanol (15 ml) for half an hour. The reaction was cooled and the separated Schiff base recrystallised from ethanol to give shining crystals (mps and analytical data in the Table).

Physiological testing : For the antibacterial testing the nutrient broth was prepared from beef extract known as "Lablemco" and was used as the culture medium. Tube dilution method^{1,3} was adopted to evaluate the activity. Czepek's medium prepared from sucrose, agar, potassium dihydrogen phosphate and magnesium sulphate was employed for the fungistatic activity. The activity was assessed by the reduction in radial growth measurement technique^{1,4}.

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TABLE*—MELTING POINTS AND ANALYTICAL DATA**

Sl. No.	Ar	(A) Amides		% Nitrogen	
		Ar'	MP (°C)	Calcd.	Found
1.	Phenyl	Methyl	160	11.6	11.5
2.	Phenyl	2-Furyl	165	9.5	9.5
3.	Phenyl	5-Bromo-2-benzofuryl	260	6.6	6.4
4.	<i>o</i> -Chloro phenyl	Phenyl	173	8.3	8.1
5.	Phenyl	<i>o</i> -Chloro phenyl	186	8.3	8.4
(B) Schiff bases					
6.	Phenyl	Phenyl	100	9.7	9.6
7.	Styryl	Phenyl	124	8.9	8.8
8.	Phenyl	2,4-Dichloro phenyl	136	7.8	7.9
9.	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	Phenyl	123	7.8	7.8
10.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	Phenyl	140	8.8	8.9
11.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	3 : 4-Methylene-dioxy phenyl	135	7.7	7.7

* All the melting points are uncorrected.

**All the compounds gave satisfactory carbon and hydrogen analyses.

Bact riostatic and fungistatic activity : The title compounds have showed low percentage inhibitions to both bacteria and fungi and hence were not found to be appreciably active. It must be mentioned here that almost all the substances are very sparingly soluble, and the low activity, may be attributed to this factor.

Three bacteria, namely *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Eschirichia coli* and *Bacillus subtilis* were employed as the test organisms. For the fungistatic activity the test organism was *Aspergillus niger*.

Experimental

General procedure :

I. *Preparation of 3-methyl-4-acylamino-5-styryl isoxazole (VI) :*

3-Methyl-4-amino-5-styryl isoxazole^{1,2} (.005 mole)